

DIGITAL PROCESSING OF TELEVISION IMAGES

Beknazarova Saida Safibullayevna

*Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after
Muhammad Al- Khwarizmi, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.*

Abstract. In the article describe the estimation of the accuracy of image reconstruction by lifting filters, that in video codecs, the main compression of the video stream is provided by eliminating inter-frame redundancy using motion compensation methods for image fragments of adjacent frames. However, the use of motion compensation methods requires the formation of additional data (metadata) containing information about the types of image blocks used, the coordinates of their movement, etc. At the same time, in order to increase the compression of the video stream without compromising its quality, higher accuracy of motion compensation is required, which leads to an increase in the number of blocks and, accordingly, to an increase in the volume of metadata that reduces the effectiveness of motion compensation. This is the main problem of compressing streaming video without degrading the quality of images. In addition, the higher accuracy of positioning blocks with motion compensation dramatically reduces the speed of image processing, which is not always feasible in real-time systems.

Digital image processing is a rapidly developing field of science. Research and development of methods and algorithms for processing and analyzing information presented in the form of digital images is a very urgent task.

The great contribution to the digital processing of television images was made by both domestic scientists – V.T. Fisenko [3], M.L. Mestetsky [5], V.P. Dvorkovich, A.V. Dvorkovich [1], M.K. Chobanu [5], V.N. Kozlov [3], V.N. Gridin [5], V.Yu. Visilter [4], A.L. Priorov [3], as well as by L. Shapiro [2], R. Gonzalez [4], R. Woods [1], G. Finlayson[2], C. Wöhler [4], R. Szeliski [1], D. Maier [2].

The number of fundamental studies of B.A.Alpatov, O.I Atakishchev., O.E., Bashmakov, P.E Bykov., S.B. Gurevich, R.Duda, P. Hart and others are devoted to the development of methods for detecting and tracking moving objects, image processing and control of objects and purposeful processes. Methods of digital image processing were considered in the works of R.Gonzalez, A.A. Lukyanitsa, B.C. Titov, S.A. Filist Issues related to the transmission of video data were investigated in the works of Yu.B. Zubarev, Yu.S. Sogdulaev, etc. Methods of recognition of static and dynamic images based on spatio-temporal analysis of video images were covered in the works of M.N. Favorskaya, V.A. Soifer, V.T. Fisenko, D. Foresight, I.A. Klyuchikov, etc. At the same time, the issues of recognition of moving people (dynamic images) in various situations and in conditions of changing factors (interference, lighting heterogeneity, change of angle, etc.) remain unresolved.

The analysis of the literature has shown that the systems using algorithms of applied television are of the greatest interest. Such systems use the visible part of the electromagnetic spectrum, which is convenient for practical use [2-3]. To date, applied television systems are widely used to perform various kinds of measurement work: diagnostics of the road network [1-2]; detection of pedestrians [2]; detection of obstacles on the runway [2-4]; collision prevention on railways [2-5]; detection of obstacles in front of a mobile ground object [1-5]. All the listed systems using the methods of applied television to perform their task analyze a specific type of obstacle, without solving the problem in the general case. In this regard, a

system of applied television based on digital image processing is proposed to solve the problem of detecting obstacles in the room by an autonomous mobile robotic platform, which characterizes in such an obstacle, the system is the main color feature, information, which makes it possible to distinguish the types of the underlying surface.

The purpose of the scientific article is to develop models, methods and algorithms for processing complex structured video data based on the use of methods to increase the contrast of television images in video information systems.

Frequency methods of image transformations are based on the idea of the Fourier transform, the meaning of which is to represent the original function as a sum of trigonometric functions of various frequencies multiplied by specified coefficients. An important property is that the function represented by the Fourier transform, after performing transformations on it, can be returned to its original form. This approach allows you to process the function in the frequency domain, and then return to the original form without loss of information. The Fourier transform can also be used to solve image filtering problems. In a practical application, the implementation of frequency approaches can be similar to spatial filtering methods.

Spatial image enhancement techniques are applied to raster images represented as two-dimensional matrices. The principle of spatial algorithms is to apply special operators to each point of the original image. Rectangular or square matrices called masks, kernels or windows act as operators. Most often, the mask is a small two-dimensional array, and improvement methods based on this approach are often called mask processing or mask filtering.

Usually, images are distorted under the influence of various kinds of interference. This complicates both their visual analysis by a specialist and automatic processing using computer technology. Attenuation of the interference effect can be achieved using various image filtering methods. When filtering, the brightness of each point of the source image distorted by interference is replaced by some other brightness value, which is assumed to be distorted to a lesser extent. Such a decision can be made based on the following considerations. The image is represented by a two-dimensional function of spatial coordinates, the values of which change more slowly when moving from point to point of the image than the values of a two-dimensional function describing interference. This allows, when evaluating the value of the useful signal at each point of the image, to take into account a certain set of neighboring points, taking advantage of a certain degree of similarity of the useful signal at these points.

Therefore, in video codecs, the main compression of the video stream is provided by eliminating inter-frame redundancy using motion compensation methods for image fragments of adjacent frames. However, the use of motion compensation methods requires the formation of additional data (metadata) containing information about the types of image blocks used, the coordinates of their movement, etc. At the same time, in order to increase the compression of the video stream without compromising its quality, higher accuracy of motion compensation is required, which leads to an increase in the number of blocks and, accordingly, to an increase in the volume of metadata that reduces the effectiveness of motion compensation. This is the main problem of compressing streaming video without degrading the quality of images. In addition, the higher accuracy of positioning blocks with motion compensation dramatically reduces the speed of image processing, which is not always feasible in real-time systems. Therefore, MPEG-4-10 codecs use a rectangular block structure of variable size, which provides acceptable image quality at speeds of more than 3 Mbit/s. Thus, the main problem of compressing a video stream without visually degrading the quality of images in real-time is the

fairly large amount of metadata required to decode compressed images. To date, this problem has not yet been fully solved in world practice.

By varying these numbers for different conversion levels and different quadrants, you can control the degree of video data loss in the image, thereby changing the compression ratio and the quality of the restored images. At the same time, to ensure the constancy of the bitrate of the compressed video stream, an adaptive change in the values of the quantization coefficients is used, which maintains the constancy of the frame compression ratio when excessive information changes in them. At the same time, the quantization coefficients calculated in the compressor are stored in the output array for proper operation of the decompressor. However, an increase in video data compression leads to an increase in irreversible data loss, which affects the visual quality of the restored images. Therefore, determining the optimal values of the quantizer is a rather difficult task and requires further research.

One of the most urgent tasks in the field of audio-video data processing is the improvement of audio-video data compression methods, taking into account the elimination of temporary redundancy of TV images and audio accompaniment. This problem is very relevant in conditions of limited frequency resources. In addition, it becomes possible to significantly reduce the preparation time for television reports to be broadcast directly from the event sites by transmitting signals from TV cameras directly to the installation hardware of television centers over cellular networks. At the same time, there is no need to use expensive and not always available broadband communication channels.

As a result of the conducted research, TV images have code, intra-frame statistical, psychovisual, structural, temporal, or inter-frame redundancy, when eliminated, image information reduction or video data compression is achieved.

Statistical redundancy is eliminated by the use of spectral transformations based on PREP and VP and allows you to compress images by 20-20 times for PREP and 30-40 for VP, and with virtually no data loss.

The presence of psych visual redundancy allows you to control the codec compression ratio by removing that part of useful information that is either not perceived by our visual system or makes it little noticeable. This approach makes it possible to increase codec compression and, while maintaining visual quality, image compression can be obtained up to 40 times with PREP and 60-70 times with VP. However, with high compression ratios, there are noticeable image distortions in the form of a block structure in PREP or a loss of clarity in VP.

The presence of inter-frame redundancy makes it possible to further increase the compression of the video stream to about 80-90 times due to the use of various motion compensation methods. However, these methods for the correct recovery of images during decoding form an additional array of metadata carrying information, but new coordinates of the moved blocks, pointers of block types, etc. Metadata is added to the compressed image data in a single digital stream and must be protected from possible errors, otherwise, it will not be possible to restore the image. Moreover, to ensure a higher compression ratio, a more accurate operation of the motion compensator is required by reducing the size of the blocks, changing their geometry, or adapting their shape to the configuration of the video objects of the scene (adaptive compensation). However, this leads to a significant increase in the volume of metadata, and accordingly to a decrease in the resulting compression ratio of the video stream,

negating all the advantages of motion compensation. Therefore, increased compression can only be achieved by degrading the quality of the images.

Fractal compression methods based on the elimination of structural redundancy can provide the required compression of the video stream by 150-200 times, but they have very low performance and currently cannot provide real-time processing of the video stream [5].

Thus, to date, existing image processing algorithms can only achieve 130-150 times compression of the video stream due to a noticeable deterioration in their visual quality. Therefore, to ensure good quality of TV images with a frame size of 8-10 kBytes, it is necessary to develop new effective methods for processing video streams that significantly minimize the amount of metadata (no more than 500 bytes per frame), or do not use motion compensation at all.

Experimental evaluation of the efficiency of compression of audio files by fractal and fractal-spectral codec. To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed method of audio signal compression based on the elimination of temporary redundancy of audio frames, an experimental study of the compression of audio files of various genres with various errors in the identification of audio frames was conducted.

Currently, Haar wavelets are widely used for information compression, which is characterized by simplicity of implementation, since it has only 2 coefficients. However, the Haar wavelet is not very suitable for compressing audio signals, because it does not provide a high degree of compression of the ZS, since when a large number of conversion coefficients are discarded, distortions occur in the form of extraneous noise, crackling and rumbling. To eliminate this disadvantage, higher-order wavelets can be used, for example, Daubeshi-4th order, having 4 coefficients and Daubeshi-10, having 10 coefficients [4,14]. Moreover, the functions of higher-order wavelets have a more "smooth" shape, due to which the compression ratio can be increased while maintaining the sound quality. Therefore, for the implementation of the compression algorithm, it is most advisable to use the Dobschy wavelet of the 10th order, since on the one hand, it provides greater conversion accuracy, and on the other, it does not significantly reduce the processing speed.

REFERENCES

- Y. Pan, X. Guo, H. Lin, and S. Luo, *Proceedings of 2020 ACM International Conference Proceeding Series* (Association for Computing Machinery, Ottawa, 2020), pp. 130-133.
- E. A. Lomtev, M. G. Myasnikova, N. V. Myasnikova, and B. V. Tsylin, *Measurement techniques* **58**, 250-255 (2015).
- S. Beknazarova, R. Bazhenov, A. Zatonkiy. Advantages of Freeware-based Simulation Tools for Technical and Technological Modeling/ Conference: 2021 International Conference on Industrial Engineering, Applications and Manufacturing (ICIEAM) DOI:10.1109/ICIEAM51226.2021.9446186.
- F. Cappello, S. Di, S. Li, X. Liang, A. M. Gok, D. Tao, C. H. Yoon, X. C. Wu, Y. Alexeev, and F. T. Chong, *International Journal of High Performance Computing Applications* **33**, 1201-1220 (2019).
- D. Tao, S. Di, Z. Chen, and F. Cappello, *IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium (IPDPS)* (IEEE, Orlando, 2017), pp. 1129-1139.